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INNOVATIVE METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH

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Annotation: *The article highlights various methods of teaching English, as well as describes the use of innovative methods of teaching students' communication in English. New methods such as group discussions, role-playing games, brainstorming, etc., help students to increase confidence in the process of communication in English.*

Keywords: *english, innovation, methods, learning through experience, cross-learning.*

Currently, English is the language of international, global communication. It is the existence of such a universal means of communication that prevents social isolation and opens up new opportunities for personal development. English is rightfully considered the most widely spoken language in the world and is most often used as a tool for cultural and educational exchange. Now, in many countries, learning English is becoming mandatory not only at the local level, but also at the global level of education.

The methodology of teaching foreign languages is an extremely important, but insufficiently disclosed topic today. In the era of globalization and technological progress, information civilization dictates new standards, knowledge is rapidly becoming obsolete. The younger generation lives in conditions of constant change, and «education must keep up with the times». It is possible to organize the learning process of representatives of generation Z as effectively as possible only with the help of innovative educational methods [1].

In general, innovative language teaching involves the teacher's creative approach to explaining the material. Teaching should include two main components: sending and receiving information. The main task of any teacher is to attract the attention of students and convey their ideas in such a way that students memorize the material for a long time and use it for subsequent work. For this to happen, it is necessary to review the classroom experience and introduce innovative methods that will make the teaching process more effective.

There are various tools for attracting student's attention:

- a) audio and video tools;
- b) brainstorming (a method of collective problem solving) (brainstorm);
- c) classes outside the classroom;
- d) role-playing games;
- e) puzzles and games.

The use of audiovisual materials, textbooks with models and diagrams, filmstrips, films, infographics and other graphic materials in the classroom develops the student's imagination. Why is this so important? According to the pedagogical terminology dictionary, imagination is a fantasy, a mental process that consists in creating images of existing and non-existent objects. This type of mental activity is based on memory and logical thinking and allows a person to control emotions, conduct thought experiments, considering the best possible scenario for themselves, set goals and achieve them. In addition, visualization methods in teaching will not only increase students' interest in the topic, but also help them better understand the structure and concepts of the language.

Another method of learning is brainstorming. In the context of teaching, brainstorming is a teaching strategy or tool used by a teacher, in which all students participate, presenting different opinions on a specific given topic. This technique helps to overcome the language barrier, which is the most common problem when learning English, and also encourages ideas and suggestions expressed by students. Teamwork also helps to build stress tolerance and self-confidence.

First, the class is divided into small groups. The teacher presents a specific question or topic in English and encourages students to think about the problem and express their ideas. Criticism of other people's opinions is prohibited. The ideas of each student should be listened to and accepted without any negative judgments or other comments. During the allotted time, the teacher oversees the group assignment and ensures that students speak only English to each other. This method encourages students' creativity and increases their motivation.

The next tool for attracting students' attention is classes outside the classroom. For example, during a visit to a museum or park, the thematic vocabulary associated with the place of study is absorbed by the trainees much more effectively. This method involves active cooperation between students and is designed to improve their communication skills, as well as monologue skills. Trainees will find this approach fresh and exciting.

Role-playing classes are a great way to get students to step out of their comfort zone and develop interpersonal communication skills. In the lesson, the teacher simulates an ordinary situation (for example, meeting old school friends, buying plane tickets, etc.) and allocates a few minutes to prepare a dialogue. Then, students present their own scenarios in pairs, consolidating new vocabulary during immersion in the language environment.

Puzzles and games. When puzzles and games are part of education, learning is combined with entertainment (Edutainment). Puzzles, board games, and crosswords in English help students think creatively and cope with difficulties. During the game, the student's attention is focused not on the language being used, but on the message being conveyed to other participants. Ignoring the correctness of the language forms, most students do their best to win. The main purpose of this method is to get students talking, stimulate their imagination, curiosity, and interest in language.

In conclusion, it should be noted that an English teacher in the 21st century should abandon traditional teaching concepts and adopt the latest, innovative methods. English language teachers should not only understand the discipline, but also be resourceful and creative, able to interest the student and explain the material clearly. The introduction of interactive learning and the changing role of education are inevitable with the development of multimedia and the emergence of a technologically savvy generation of young people [3].

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